

A Dynamic Temporal Logic for Quality of Service in Choreographic Models *

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Abstract We propose a framework for expressing and analyzing the *Quality of Service* (QoS) of message-passing systems using a choreographic model that consists of *g-choreographies* and *Communicating Finite State machines* (CFSMs). The following are our three main contributions: (I) an extension of CFSMs with non-functional contracts to specify quantitative constraints of local computations, (II) a dynamic temporal logic capable of expressing QoS, properties of systems relative to the *g-choreography* that specifies the communication protocol, (III) the semi-decidability of our logic which enables a bounded model-checking approach to verify QoS property of communicating systems.

1 Introduction

Over the past two decades, software has steadily changed from monolithic applications to distributed cooperating components. Choreographic approaches are gaining momentum in industry (e.g. [1,2,3,5]) which, increasingly, conceives applications as components interacting over existing communication infrastructures. Among other models, choreographies stand out for a neat separation of concerns: choreographic models abstract away local computations from communications among participants. In fact, since their introduction [6], choreographies

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range?” or “is the monetary overall monetary cost below a given threshold?”. Answers to such questions require checking that the *aggregation* of the constraints on the quality attributes along the run π entails the properties. Interestingly, how to aggregate those constraints depends on the quality attributes. For instance, the aggregation of memory consumption can be computed by taking the maximum, while the aggregation of monetary cost can be computed as the sum. We work under the hypothesis that developers have no control over communication infrastructure. More precisely, QoS aspects related to how communications are realised are not under the control of applications’ designers. Instead, designers have control over local computations, thus suggesting that QoS constraints are naturally associated to states of components. Indeed, we rely on behavioural types (such as [9,10,11,12,13]) which abstract away low level details.

Contributions We propose a framework for the design and analysis of QoS-aware distributed systems, enabled by the following technical contributions:

Models for QoS attributes. Section 4 presents a straightforward extension of communicating finite-state machines (CFSMs [14]; reviewed in Section 3) to express QoS aspects of components. Basically, we assign to each state of CFSMs a QoS specification as in (1).

We adopt real-closed fields (RCFs, cf. Section 3) to abstractly represent QoS values; besides being a complete and decidable abstract formalisation of the first-order theory of the real numbers, RCFs are instrumental for a smooth definition of our framework.

A dynamic temporal logic for QoS. Section 5 introduces a logic, dubbed \mathcal{QL} , to express QoS properties. Taking inspiration from *Propositional Dynamic Linear Temporal Logic* (DLTL) [15], \mathcal{QL} indexes temporal modalities with *global choreographies* [16] (g-choreographies, Section 3), a model of global views of choreographies, in order to predicate over QoS properties of the whole system. This is a distinct characteristic of \mathcal{QL} that we comment in Section 2.

A semi-decision procedure for \mathcal{QL} . Section 6 proves \mathcal{QL} to be semi-decidable by providing a k -bounded semi-decision procedure and relying on the decidability of the theory of real-closed fields [17] to check QoS constraints in atomic formulae. A distinctive aspect of the procedure is that it can be used as a bounded model-checking procedure where the bound is established by the g-choreographies indexing the modalities of \mathcal{QL} formulae.

Section 7 draws some conclusions and points out some further lines of research.

2 Related Work

The relevance of the problem addressed here has been already highlighted by other researchers [7,8]. There is a vast literature on QoS, spanning a wide range of contexts and methods [18,19]. This paper can be positioned in the category of general application-level QoS. The combination of RCFs and our behavioural

types aims to capture essential aspects for applications’ quantitative analysis while striving for generality. In this vein, a proof-of-concept methodology based on behavioural types has been proposed in [20] for client-server systems. To the best of our knowledge, ours is the first work blending behavioural types with QoS and offering a decision procedure for multiparty protocols.

In order to abstractly capture QoS (instead of focusing on specific attributes) we adopt RCFs. Other abstract models of QoS such as quantales [21] or c-semirings [22,23,24] have been proposed. We opted for RCFs due to their inherent decidability, which is crucial for ensuring the decidability of our logic. Moreover, RCFs offer practical advantages as they can be readily employed in modern SMT (satisfiability modulo theories) solvers [41, Chapter 33].

Theory presentations over QoS attributes are used in [25] to enable the automatic analysis of QoS properties with a specification language that only considers convex polytopes; this restriction is not present in our language. Also, the approach in [25] can be thought as “monolithic”, in the sense that specifications are given considering the system as a black box. We instead assign QoS contracts to states of components and then aggregate them in order to analyze properties along executions of the behavior emerging from interactions.

The use of choreographic methods for non-functional analysis yields other advantages. For instance, QoS contracts of components are derived from global specifications [7]. These contracts can then be used for run-time prediction, adaptive composition, or compliance checking, similarly to what is done in [8]. This top-down approach can be transferred to behavioural types as well similarly to what has been done in [11,26] for qualitative properties. The framework proposed in [27] uses CFSMs as a dynamic binding mechanism of services but only considers the communicational aspects of the software component. Such a framework could be extended to include QoS attributes as well by leveraging the results presented in this paper.

Our QL logic takes inspiration from *dynamic linear temporal logic (DLTL)* [15] which blends trace semantics (akin *linear temporal logic* [28]) and regular expressions over a set of atomic actions (akin *propositional dynamic logic* [29]). Intuitively a key difference is that, unlike *DLTL*, QL does not predicate about the behaviour of sequential programs; rather QL describes properties of asynchronous message-passing systems. This requires a modification of the syntax of *DLTL*; in fact, the syntax of QL is essentially the same of *DLTL* barred for the indexes of modalities, which become choreographies of interactions. This straightforward modification has deep impact on the semantics which requires a complete redefinition (see Section 7 for further details). Another key difference is that, while *DLTL* is propositional, QL ’s atomic formulae are first order formulae on QoS attributes. As a consequence, not only QL can express usual temporal properties, such as safety and liveness ones, but temporal properties constraining the value of QoS attributes. These points of comparison with *DLTL* apply in the same way to a similar logic called *linear dynamic logic (LDL)*, introduced first in [30] and later formalized for finite traces in [31].

3 Preliminaries

This section surveys background material underpinning our work. We first describe the protocol used as a running example, then we review our choreographic model and we briefly recall *real-closed fields*.

A running example. Through the paper we will use a (simplified variant) of the POP protocol [32]. This protocol allows mail clients to access a remote mailbox and retrieve e-mails. In the POP protocol a client starts the communication by sending a message of type **helo** to a POP server (note that protocol specifications are oblivious of messages' payload).⁵ The server replies with the number of unread messages in the mailbox using a message of type **int**. At this point the client can either halt the protocol or read one of the e-mails. These options are selected by sending a message of type **quit** or of type **read** respectively. In the former case, the server acknowledges with a message of type **bye** and the protocol ends. In the latter case, the server sends the client the number of bytes of the current unread message in a message of type **size**. Next, the client has again a choice between quitting the protocol (as before) or receiving the email (selected in the **read** message) by sending the server a message of type **retr**. In the latter case the server sends the email with a message of type **msg**, the client answers with a message of type **ack** and the reading process starts again.

A choreographic model. We use *global choreographies* [16] to specify the global view of communicating systems whose local view are rendered as *communicating finite state machines* [14].

Hereafter, we fix a set \mathcal{P} of *participants* and a set \mathcal{M} of (types of) *messages* such that $\mathcal{P} \cap \mathcal{M} = \emptyset$. We start by surveying the definition of g-choreographies.

Definition 1 (Global choreographies [16]). A global choreography over \mathcal{P} and \mathcal{M} (g-choreography for short) is a term G that can be derived in

$$G ::= \mathbf{0} \mid A \rightarrow B : m \mid G; G' \mid G \mid G' \mid G + G' \mid G^*$$

where $A, B \in \mathcal{P}$, $A \neq B$ and $m \in \mathcal{M}$.

Intuitively, a g-choreography specifies the communication protocol of participants. The basic g-choreography is the empty one $\mathbf{0}$, which specifies that no communications should happen. An *interaction* $A \rightarrow B : m$ specifies that participants A and B (are expected to) exchange a message of type m ; it is worth remarking that we assume asynchronous communication where the sender A does not wait for B to consume m to continue its execution. Moreover, g-choreographies can be composed sequentially ($G; G'$), in parallel ($G \mid G'$), and in non-deterministic choices ($G + G'$); we assume that $\mathbf{0}$ is the neutral element of $;$, \mid , $+$, and $+$. Note that, due to asynchrony in the communication, in a sequential composition $G; G'$, outputs in G' can occur before G is fully executed; for instance, the distributed execution of $A \rightarrow B : m; C \rightarrow B : m'$ allows the output from C to happen before the one from A . Finally, a g-choreography may be iterated (G^*).

⁵ Our framework can handle multiparty protocols; however, our examples are two-party for simplicity. Also, we stick to the types of messages as carefully described in the protocol specifications [32].

Example 1 (A g-choreography for POP). Our running example can be expressed as the g-choreography $G_{\text{pop}} = C \rightarrow S: \text{helo}; G_{\text{start}} + G_{\text{quit}}$ where

$$\begin{array}{ll} G_{\text{start}} = S \rightarrow C: \text{int}; (G_{\text{read}} + G_{\text{read}}; G_{\text{retr}})^*; G_{\text{quit}} & G_{\text{read}} = C \rightarrow S: \text{read}; S \rightarrow C: \text{size} \\ G_{\text{retr}} = C \rightarrow S: \text{retr}; S \rightarrow C: \text{msg}; C \rightarrow S: \text{ack} & G_{\text{quit}} = C \rightarrow S: \text{quit}; S \rightarrow C: \text{bye} \end{array}$$

($;$ takes precedence over $+$).

The participants of a communicating system interact through *channels* borrowed from the set $\mathcal{C} = \{(A, B) \in \mathcal{P} \times \mathcal{P} \mid A \neq B\}$. A channel $(A, B) \in \mathcal{C}$ (written AB for short) allows A to asynchronously send messages to B through an unbounded FIFO buffer associated to AB . The set of *communication actions* is $\mathcal{L} = \mathcal{L}^! \cup \mathcal{L}^?$ where $\mathcal{L}^! = \{AB!m \mid AB \in \mathcal{C} \text{ and } m \in \mathcal{M}\}$ and $\mathcal{L}^? = \{AB?m \mid AB \in \mathcal{C} \text{ and } m \in \mathcal{M}\}$ are respectively the set of *output* and *input* actions. The *language* $\mathcal{L}[G]$ of a g-choreography G is essentially the set of all possible sequences in \mathcal{L} compatible with the causal relation induced by G . Since $\mathcal{L}[G]$ is prefix-closed, we write $\hat{\mathcal{L}}[G]$ for the set of sequences in $\mathcal{L}[G]$ that are not proper prefixes of any other sequence in $\mathcal{L}[G]$. The technical definition of $\mathcal{L}[G]$, immaterial here, can be found in [16]. We will adapt CFSM [14] to model the QoS-aware *local view* of a system.

Definition 2 (Communicating systems [14]). A communicating finite-state machine (CFSM) is a finite transition system $M = (Q, q_0, \rightarrow)$ where

- Q is a finite set of states with $q_0 \in Q$ the initial state, and
- $\rightarrow \subseteq Q \times \mathcal{L} \times Q$; we write $q \xrightarrow{\ell} q'$ for $(q, \ell, q') \in \rightarrow$.

For $AB!m \in \mathcal{L}$ (resp. $AB?m \in \mathcal{L}$), let $\text{subj}(AB!m) = A$ (resp. $\text{subj}(AB?m) = B$). Given $A \in \mathcal{P}$, M is A -local if $\text{subj}(\ell) = A$ for each $q \xrightarrow{\ell} q'$. A (communicating) system is a map $S = (M_A)_{A \in \mathcal{P}}$ assigning a A -local CFSM M_A to each $A \in \mathcal{P}$.

Example 2 (Communicating system for POP). The following CFSM exhibits a behaviour of a POP client compatible with the protocol in Example 1 because its executions yield a subset of the client's execution specified there.

For a POP server, being a two-party protocol, we can use a dual CFSM obtained by replacing send actions with corresponding receive actions and vice versa. \diamond

The asynchronous communication between participants is formalised by a labelled transition system (LTS) tracking the (local) state of each CFSM and the content of each buffer (i.e. communication channel) in the system. A *configuration* of a communicating system S is a pair $s = \langle \mathbf{q}; \mathbf{b} \rangle$ where \mathbf{q} and \mathbf{b} respectively map participants to states and channels to sequences of messages;

state $q(\mathbf{A})$ keeps track of the state of the machine $M_{\mathbf{A}}$ and buffer $\mathfrak{b}(\mathbf{A}\mathbf{B})$ yields the messages sent from \mathbf{A} to \mathbf{B} and not yet consumed. The *initial* configuration s_0 is the one where, for all $\mathbf{A} \in \mathcal{P}$, $q(\mathbf{A})$ is the initial state of the corresponding CFMS and $\mathfrak{b}(\mathbf{A}\mathbf{B})$ is the empty sequence for all $\mathbf{A}\mathbf{B} \in \mathcal{C}$.

A configuration $s' = \langle \mathbf{q}' ; \mathfrak{b}' \rangle$ is *reachable* from another configuration $s = \langle \mathbf{q} ; \mathfrak{b} \rangle$ by *firing a transition* ℓ , written $s \xrightarrow{\ell} s'$, if there is a message $\mathfrak{m} \in \mathcal{M}$ such that either (1) or (2) below holds:

1. $\ell = \mathbf{A}\mathbf{B}!\mathfrak{m}$ with $q(\mathbf{A}) \xrightarrow{\ell}_{\mathbf{A}} q'$ and
 - a. $\mathbf{q}' = \mathbf{q}[\mathbf{A} \mapsto q']$
 - b. $\mathfrak{b}' = \mathfrak{b}[\mathbf{A}\mathbf{B} \mapsto \mathfrak{b}(\mathbf{A}\mathbf{B}).\mathfrak{m}]$
2. $\ell = \mathbf{A}\mathbf{B}?\mathfrak{m}$ with $q(\mathbf{B}) \xrightarrow{\ell}_{\mathbf{B}} q'$ and
 - a. $\mathbf{q}' = \mathbf{q}[\mathbf{B} \mapsto q']$ and
 - b. $\mathfrak{b} = \mathfrak{b}'[\mathbf{A}\mathbf{B} \mapsto \mathfrak{m}.\mathfrak{b}'(\mathbf{A}\mathbf{B})]$.

Condition (1) puts \mathfrak{m} on channel $\mathbf{A}\mathbf{B}$, while (2) gets \mathfrak{m} from channel $\mathbf{A}\mathbf{B}$. In both cases, any machine or buffer not involved in the transition is left unchanged in the new configuration s' .

Example 3 (Semantics of CFMSs). For the run π of the communicating system in (1) (cf. Section 1) we have, for $i \in \{0, 1, 2\}$, $s_i = \langle \mathbf{q}_i ; \mathfrak{b}_i \rangle$, where $\mathbf{q}_0 = \{\mathbf{A} \mapsto q_0, \mathbf{B} \mapsto q_0'\}$, $\mathfrak{b}_0 = \{\mathbf{A}\mathbf{B} \mapsto \epsilon, \mathbf{B}\mathbf{A} \mapsto \epsilon\}$, $\mathbf{q}_1 = \{\mathbf{A} \mapsto q_1, \mathbf{B} \mapsto q_0'\}$, $\mathfrak{b}_1 = \{\mathbf{A}\mathbf{B} \mapsto \mathfrak{m}, \mathbf{B}\mathbf{A} \mapsto \epsilon\}$, and $\mathbf{q}_2 = \{\mathbf{A} \mapsto q_1, \mathbf{B} \mapsto q_1'\}$, $\mathfrak{b}_2 = \mathfrak{b}_0$. \diamond

Let S be a communicating system. A sequence $\pi = (s_i, \ell_i, s_{i+1})_{i \in I}$ where I is an initial segment of natural numbers (i.e., $i-1 \in I$ for each $0 < i \in I$) is a run of S if $s_i \xrightarrow{\ell_i} s_{i+1}$ is a transition of S for all $i \in I$. The set of runs of S is denoted as Δ_S^∞ and the set of runs of length k is denoted as Δ_S^k . Note that Δ_S^∞ may contain runs of infinite length, the set of finite runs of S is the union of all Δ_S^k and will be denoted as Δ_S . Given a run π , we define $\mathcal{L}[\pi]$ to be the sequence of labels $(\ell_i)_{i \in I}$. The *language* of S is the set $\mathcal{L}[S] = \{\mathcal{L}[\pi] \mid \pi \in \Delta_S^\infty\}$. Finally, $\text{prf} : \Delta_S^\infty \rightarrow 2^{\Delta_S}$ maps each run $\pi \in \Delta_S^\infty$ to its set of finite prefixes. As usual, for all $\pi \in \Delta_S^\infty$, the empty prefix ϵ belongs to $\text{prf}(\pi)$. For convenience, we will occasionally write $s_0 \xrightarrow{\ell_0} s_1 \dots s_n \xrightarrow{\ell_n} s_{n+1}$ for finite sequences.

Real-closed fields. Real numbers are natural candidates to express quantitative attributes of a software artifact. We adopt *real-closed fields* (RCFs), which is the formalisation of the first-order theory of the real numbers, as a foundation for QoS values. Let Σ_{field} denote the first-order signature $\langle \{0, 1\}, \{+, \cdot\}, \{<\} \rangle$. An ordered field is a first-order theory presentation $\langle \Sigma_{\text{field}}, \Gamma_{\text{field}} \rangle$, where Γ_{field} consists of the *field* axioms as well as the axioms defining $<$ as a strict total order relation. Real-closed fields are ordered fields whose non-empty subsets all have a supremum. Tarski's axiomatization of real-closed fields, denoted here as $\langle \Sigma_{\text{RCF}}, \Gamma_{\text{RCF}} \rangle$, was introduced in [17]. Tarski further demonstrated the existence of a decision procedure for this first-order theory of real numbers in [17, Thm. 37]. Thus, the main reason for selecting RCFs as the foundation for QoS lies in the fact that first-order theories extending them using elementary operations are decidable, providing effective means for analysis.

4 Quality of Service of Communicating Systems

In this section we extend CFSMs with QoS specifications in order to express QoS contracts of components in message-passing systems. Basically, each state of CFSMs is assigned a QoS contract specifying the usage of computational resources. We formalise QoS contracts as *QoS specifications* which are theory presentations over the RCFs, noted as $\langle \Sigma, \Gamma \rangle$, paired up with *aggregation operators*, noted as \oplus^a , to define how each QoS attribute accumulates along a communicating system. These aggregation operators will be essential to formally define the notion of aggregation along a run, as shown later in Example 9.

Definition 3. A QoS specification $\langle \Sigma, \Gamma \rangle$ is a (first-order) theory presentation extending $\langle \Sigma_{\text{RCF}}, \Gamma_{\text{RCF}} \rangle$ as follows:

1. $\Sigma = \langle \{0, 1\} \cup \mathbf{Q}, \{+, \cdot\} \cup \{\oplus^a\}_{a \in \mathbf{Q}}, \{<\} \rangle$, where \mathbf{Q} is a finite set of constant symbols (other than 0 and 1) representing the quantitative attributes (from now on referred to as QoS attributes) and, for each $a \in \mathbf{Q}$, \oplus^a is an associative algebraic binary operator and
2. $\Gamma = \Gamma_{\text{RCF}} \cup \Gamma'$, being Γ' a finite set of first-order formulae formalising specific constraints over the QoS attributes in \mathbf{Q} .

The class of QoS specifications will be denoted as $\mathcal{C}(\mathbf{Q})$.

In order to preserve decidability of QoS properties, we only consider QoS specifications involving additional constant symbols representing the QoS attributes of components. Aggregation operators are required to be algebraic because the extension of the theory must be kept in the first-order fragment (uninterpreted function or predicate symbols must be avoided to preserve decidability). It is worth noticing that aggregation operators strongly depend on the nature of each specific attribute; for example, natural aggregation operators for memory and time are the maximum function and sum respectively.

Example 4 (QoS specification). With reference to Example 2, possible quantitative attributes of interest in an implementation of POP are $\mathbf{Q} = \{t, c, m\}$ representing CPU time, monetary cost, and memory usage, respectively. Then a QoS specification that characterises low computational costs, where no internal process consumes significant amount of resources, can be written according to Definition 3 as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \Sigma &= \langle \{0, 1\} \cup \{t, c, m\}, \{+, \cdot\} \cup \{\oplus^t, \oplus^c, \oplus^m\}, \{<\} \rangle \\ \Gamma &= \Gamma_{\text{RCF}} \cup \Gamma'_{\text{Low}} \end{aligned}$$

where $\oplus^t = +$, $\oplus^c = +$, $\oplus^m = \max$, and $\Gamma'_{\text{Low}} = \{t \leq .01, c \leq .01, m \leq .01\}$ \diamond

From now on, we fix a set of constant symbols \mathbf{Q} which we omit from the set of *QoS specifications*, that will be referred to just as \mathcal{C} . It is worth noting that, when \mathbf{Q} is fixed, a QoS specification $\langle \Sigma, \Gamma_{\text{RCF}} \cup \Gamma' \rangle$, is completely determined by Γ' . Therefore, we can unambiguously refer to a QoS specification using its set of formulas Γ' . Thus, the QoS specification in Example 4 is Γ'_{Low} .

Example 5 (QoS for POP). The following QoS specifications formalise the costs associated to different activities in the POP protocol of Example 2.

$$\Gamma'_{\text{Chk}} = \{t \leq 5, c = 0.5, m = 0\}$$

$$\Gamma'_{\text{Mem}} = \{1 \leq t \leq 6, c = 0, m \leq 64\}$$

$$\Gamma'_{\text{DB}} = \{t \leq 3 \implies (\exists x)(0.5 \leq x \leq 1 \wedge c = t \cdot x), t > 3 \implies c = 10, m \leq 5\}$$

Basically, Γ'_{Chk} formalizes the costs associated to the activity of integrity checking a message, Γ'_{Mem} to the activity of a server receiving a message, and Γ'_{DB} to establishing that the monetary cost is fixed if the insertion takes more than three time-units and it is a fraction of the execution time, otherwise. \diamond

We now extend communicating systems (cf. Section 3) with QoS-specifications.

Definition 4 (QoS-extended CFSMs). A QoS-extended CFSM is a tuple $M^{QoS} = \langle M, F, qos \rangle$ where:

- $M = \langle Q, q_0, \rightarrow \rangle$ is a CFSM,
- $F \subseteq Q$ is a set of final states of M , and
- $qos : Q \rightarrow \mathcal{C}$ maps states of M to QoS specifications.

A QoS-extended communicating system S^{QoS} is a map $(M_A^{QoS})_{A \in \mathcal{P}}$ assigning an A -local QoS-extended CFSM M_A^{QoS} to each $A \in \mathcal{P}$. A configuration $\langle \mathbf{q} ; \mathbf{b} \rangle$ of S^{QoS} is a final configuration if $\mathbf{q}(A) \in F_A$ for every $A \in \mathcal{P}$.

Example 6 (QoS-extended CFSMs). An extended CFSM of the POP client in Example 2 with the QoS specifications of Example 5 is as follows:

where the filled state is the only final state. Each state is assigned a QoS specification given in Example 5 according to the following idea. States where the client performs negligible computations are assigned the QoS specification Γ'_{Low} . The remaining states are assigned QoS specifications as follows. The local states where C performs a database insertion (right after receiving an **int** or **size** message) and those where C accesses the memory (right before receiving an unread e-mail) are constrained respectively by Γ'_{DB} and Γ'_{Mem} ; finally, Γ'_{Chk} constrains the states where C performs an integrity check (right after receiving an unread e-mail). \diamond

Notice that Definition 4 requires every state of a CFSM to be assigned a QoS specification. However, in most cases, most states will have the same QoS specification, as it is the case of Γ'_{Low} in Example 6; typically one only has to identify the QoS costs specific to few states.

The semantics of QoS-extended communicating systems is defined in the same way as the semantics of communicating systems. This is a consequence of the fact that QoS specifications do not have any effect on communications.

5 \mathcal{QL} : A Dynamic Logic for QoS

To describe QoS properties we introduce \mathcal{QL} , a logical language akin *DLTL*.

Definition 5 (QoS formulae). *The QoS logic \mathcal{QL} consists of the smallest set of formulae that can be obtained from the following grammar:*

$$\Phi ::= \top \mid \psi \mid \neg\Phi \mid \Phi \vee \Phi \mid \Phi \mathcal{U}^G \Phi$$

where ψ is a formula in a theory presentation in \mathcal{C} , and G is a g -choreography over \mathcal{P} and \mathcal{M} (see Definition 1).

Atomic formulae express constraints over quantitative attributes. Akin *DLTL*, properties of runs are linear temporal formulae where the until operator is indexed with a global choreography G . In essence, the role of G is to restrict the set of runs to be considered for the satisfiability of the until. Global choreographies are suitable for this purpose because they are a declarative and compact way of characterizing the behaviour of asynchronous message-passing systems. The possibility modality $\langle G \rangle \Phi$ is defined as $\top \mathcal{U}^G \Phi$ and the necessity modality $[G] \Phi$ is defined (dually) as $\neg \langle G \rangle \neg \Phi$. Finally, propositional connectives \wedge and \implies are defined as usual.

The following example shows how to express non-functional properties of specific runs of the system in \mathcal{QL} .

Example 7 (QoS properties of POP protocol). We can use the g -choreographies and the \mathcal{QL} formula below to state that, unless the cost is zero for the first three e-mails read, the cost is bounded by 10 times the CPU time, and the memory consumption is bounded by 5. We define

$$\begin{aligned} \Phi &\equiv [G_3](c > 0) \implies [G_3; G_{\text{msg}}^*]((c \leq t \cdot 10) \wedge (m \leq 5)) \quad \text{where} \\ G_3 &= C \rightarrow S: \text{helo}; S \rightarrow C: \text{int}; G_{\text{msg}}; G_{\text{msg}}; G_{\text{msg}} \quad \text{and} \\ G_{\text{msg}} &= C \rightarrow S: \text{read}; S \rightarrow C: \text{size}; C \rightarrow S: \text{retr}; S \rightarrow C: \text{msg}; S \rightarrow C: \text{ack} \end{aligned}$$

Intuitively, for Φ to hold, either the first three message retrievals must have zero cost in any run of the system, or on every subsequent message retrieval, the total cost and memory consumption fall within the specified bounds. \diamond

A \mathcal{QL} formula (like Φ in Example 7) can be used in quantitative analyses by *aggregating* the values of the QoS attributes along the runs of the system. More precisely, given a run π , our interpretation is that, for each transition $s_i \xrightarrow{\ell_i} s_{i+1}$ of π , the obligations stated in the QoS specification of s_i are met after aggregating QoS information along π from state s_0 up to state s_i . Therefore, a central notion in our framework is that of *aggregation function*. Given a QoS-extended communicating system S , an *aggregation function* $\text{agg}_S : \Delta_S \rightarrow \mathcal{C}$ yields a QoS specification capturing the cumulative QoS attributes along a run $\pi \in \Delta_S$ by “summing-up” QoS specifications of participants’ local states.

Example 8 (Aggregation). Recall the run π (1) from Section 1:

Let c_A^q (resp. c_B^q) denote the value of the QoS attribute c in the state q of participant **A** (resp. **B**) and likewise for the attribute m . After π , we expect $\max\{m_A^{q_0}, m_A^{q_1}, m_B^{q_0'}, m_B^{q_1'}\}$ and $c_A^{q_0} + c_A^{q_1} + c_B^{q_0'} + c_B^{q_1'}$ to respectively be the memory consumption and the overall monetary cost in s_2 . This boils down to aggregate the QoS attributes c and m using the maximization and addition operations, respectively. \diamond

Essentially, the aggregation in this case is obtained by (1) instantiating the QoS specification associated to the local state of participants (this is done by renaming attributes as in Example 8); and (2) adding an equation combining all the instances of QoS specifications. The following formula captures this intuition and exemplifies one way in which the aggregation function could be defined.

Example 9 (Aggregation). Let $S = (\langle M_A, \text{qos}_A \rangle)_{A \in \mathcal{P}}$, we define the aggregation function $\text{agg}_S : \Delta_S \rightarrow \mathcal{C}$ to be $\text{agg}_S(\pi) = f(\pi) \cup g(\pi)$ where

$$\begin{aligned}
f(\pi) &= \bigcup_{\substack{A \in \mathcal{P} \\ 0 \leq i \leq n}} \text{qos}_A(q_i(A))_{A}^{q_i(A)} \quad \text{and} \quad g(\epsilon) = \left\{ a = \left(\bigoplus_{A \in \mathcal{P}}^a a_A^{q_0(A)} \right) \mid a \in \mathbb{Q} \right\} \\
g(\pi) &= \left\{ a = \left(\bigoplus_{\substack{0 \leq i < n \\ A = \text{subj}(\ell_i)}}^a a_A^{q_i(A)} \right) \oplus^a \left(\bigoplus_{A \in \mathcal{P}}^a a_A^{q_n(A)} \right) \mid a \in \mathbb{Q} \right\} \quad \text{if } \pi \neq \epsilon
\end{aligned}$$

where $\pi = \langle q_0; \mathbf{b}_0 \rangle \xrightarrow{\ell_0} \dots \xrightarrow{\ell_{n-1}} \langle q_n; \mathbf{b}_n \rangle \in \Delta_S$, and $\Pi_A^q = \{\psi_A^q \mid \psi \in \Pi\}$ for a set of \mathcal{QL} formulae Π , and ψ_A^q is obtained by replacing each QoS attribute c with the symbol c_A^q in the atomic formula ψ . The intuition is that $f(\pi)$ collects all the QoS specifications of the local states of the participants along the run π , and $g(\pi)$ uses the aggregation operators to calculate the aggregated values of the QoS attributes in the run π . If we apply this aggregation function to the run π in Example 8, we obtain the following:

$$\begin{aligned}
f(\pi) &= \{c_A^{q_0} \leq 5, m_A^{q_0} = 0\} \cup \{5 \leq c_A^{q_1} \leq 10, m_A^{q_1} < 3\} \\
&\quad \cup \{c_B^{q_0'} = 0, m_B^{q_0'} = 0\} \cup \{10 \leq m_B^{q_1'} \leq 50, c_B^{q_1'} = 0.01 \cdot m_B^{q_1'}\} \\
g(\pi) &= \left\{ m = \max\{m_A^{q_0}, m_A^{q_1}, m_B^{q_0'}, m_B^{q_1'}\}, c = c_A^{q_0} + c_A^{q_1} + c_B^{q_0'} + c_B^{q_1'} \right\} \quad \diamond
\end{aligned}$$

It is important to emphasize that, in our conception, an aggregation function relies on a run of the system as its input. This run inherently encompasses a specific sequential ordering of the actions carried out by the participants. The aggregation operators max and $+$ used in Example 8 follow this interpretation. As will become clear in Definition 6, this interpretation is sufficient for the purposes of this paper, since it enables \mathcal{QL} to specify temporal QoS properties about runs of the system. However, one might be interested in a different kind of aggregation that is aware of local states that are executed in parallel. This may require some care and possibly to exploit truly-concurrent models, such as pomsets; this is left for future work.

The semantics of our logic is defined in terms of QoS-extended communicating systems.

Definition 6 (\mathcal{QL} semantics). *A run is terminating if its last configuration is a final conf. (see Definition 4). Given a QoS-extended communicating system S , an S -model for a QoS property Φ is a pair $\langle \pi, \pi' \rangle$, where $\pi \in \Delta_S^\infty$ is a terminating run and $\pi' \in \text{prf}(\pi)$, such that $\langle \pi, \pi' \rangle \models_S \Phi$ where the relation \models_S is*

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \pi, \pi' \rangle \models_S \Phi & \text{ iff } \text{agg}_S(\pi') \vdash_{RCF} \Phi \text{ if } \Phi \text{ is an atomic formula} \\ \langle \pi, \pi' \rangle \models_S \neg \Phi & \text{ iff } \langle \pi, \pi' \rangle \not\models_S \Phi \text{ does not hold} \\ \langle \pi, \pi' \rangle \models_S \Phi_1 \vee \Phi_2 & \text{ iff } \langle \pi, \pi' \rangle \models_S \Phi_1 \text{ or } \langle \pi, \pi' \rangle \models_S \Phi_2 \\ \langle \pi, \pi' \rangle \models_S \Phi_1 \mathcal{U}^G \Phi_2 & \text{ iff there exists } \pi'' \text{ such that } \pi' \pi'' \in \text{prf}(\pi) \text{ and } \mathcal{L}[\pi''] \in \hat{\mathcal{L}}[\mathbb{G}], \\ & \text{satisfying } \langle \pi, \pi' \pi'' \rangle \models_S \Phi_2 \text{ and, for all } \pi''' \in \text{prf}(\pi''), \\ & \text{if } \pi''' \neq \pi'' \text{ then } \langle \pi, \pi' \pi''' \rangle \models_S \Phi_1. \end{aligned}$$

A QoS property Φ is satisfiable in S if there exists a terminating run $\pi \in \Delta_S^\infty$ such that $\langle \pi, \epsilon \rangle \models_S \Phi$, and it is valid (denoted as $\models_S \Phi$) if $\langle \pi, \epsilon \rangle \models_S \Phi$ for all terminating runs $\pi \in \Delta_S^\infty$.

Negation and disjunction are handled in the standard way. The definition of the until operator is similar to the standard operator: Φ_2 must hold at some point in the future, i.e., $\pi' \pi''$ and Φ_1 must hold up to that point; the key difference is that the satisfaction of Φ_2 is restricted to runs where the extension π'' is in $\hat{\mathcal{L}}[\mathbb{G}]$. Finally, atomic formulae are handled by obtaining the aggregated QoS of the accumulated run π' and using the entailment relation of RCFs.

6 A semidecision procedure for \mathcal{QL}

We now establish the semi-decidability of \mathcal{QL} by presenting a k -bounded semi-decision procedure relying on three algorithms: qSAT , qMODELS , and qUNTIL . The qSAT algorithm is the main algorithm of the procedure and determines whether a given formula is satisfiable in a given system. It relies on qMODELS to check if there is a run that satisfies the formula which, in turn, uses qUNTIL to handle the \mathcal{U} operator. Let us start by looking at qSAT defined as

```

1 qSAT( $\Phi, S, k$ ):
2    $i = 0$ 
3   while  $i \leq k$  do
4     foreach  $\pi \in \Delta_S^i$  do
5       if  $\pi$  is a terminating run and  $\text{qMODELS}(\Phi, S, \pi, \epsilon)$  then
6         return true
7        $i = i + 1$ 
8   return false

```

Basically, `qSAT` enumerates all the runs of S up to a given bound k and checks whether any of them satisfies Φ (recall that Δ_S^i is the set of all runs of S with length i). Let us now focus on `qMODELS`:

```

1 qMODELS( $\Phi, S, \pi, \pi'$ ):
2   switch  $\Phi$  do
3     case  $\top$  do
4       return true
5     case  $\psi$  do
6       return whether  $\text{aggs}(\pi') \vdash_{RCF} \psi$ 
7     case  $\neg\Phi_1$  do
8       return not qMODELS( $\Phi_1, S, \pi, \pi'$ )
9     case  $\Phi_1 \vee \Phi_2$  do
10      return qMODELS( $\Phi_1, S, \pi, \pi'$ ) or qMODELS( $\Phi_2, S, \pi, \pi'$ )
11     case  $\Phi_1 \mathcal{U}^G \Phi_2$  do
12      return qUNTIL( $\Phi_1, G, \Phi_2, S, \pi, \pi', \epsilon$ )

```

Following Definition 6, `qMODELS` recursively inspects the \mathcal{QL} formula. It invokes `qUNTIL` to handle the \mathcal{U} operator and the decision procedure of the theory of real-closed fields to check the atomic formulae. Let us now look at `qUNTIL`:

```

1 qUNTIL( $\Phi_1, G, \Phi_2, S, \pi, \pi', \pi''$ ):
2   if  $\mathcal{L}[\pi''] \in \hat{\mathcal{L}}[G]$  and qMODELS( $\Phi_2, S, \pi, \pi', \pi''$ ) then
3     return true
4   else if not qMODELS( $\Phi_1, S, \pi, \pi', \pi''$ ) then
5     return false
6   else
7     Let  $\xrightarrow{\epsilon} q$  be the transition such that  $\pi' \pi'' \xrightarrow{\epsilon} q \in \text{prf}(\pi)$ 
8     (takes the first transition in  $\pi$  if  $\pi' \pi'' = \epsilon$ ,
9     and it is not defined if  $\pi' \pi'' = \pi$ )
10    if  $\pi' \pi'' = \pi$  or  $\mathcal{L}[\pi'' \xrightarrow{\epsilon} q] \notin \mathcal{L}[G]$  then
11      return false
12    else
13      return qUNTIL( $\Phi_1, G, \Phi_2, S, \pi, \pi', \pi'' \xrightarrow{\epsilon} q$ )

```

This procedure takes care of searching for a witness of the existential in the semantics of \mathcal{U} by starting in the current prefix π' and following the transitions of π . According to Definition 6, `qUNTIL` searches for a witness of the existential part of \mathcal{U} . It takes as parameters the complete run π , the prefix π' at which the \mathcal{U} is being evaluated, and the current extension π'' that is used to search for the witness. If π'' is enough to reach a verdict, the algorithm returns true or false accordingly (Lines 3 and 5). Otherwise, it tries to extend π'' by borrowing the next transition of π (Line 7). If such extension exists and is a candidate for being in the language of G , the algorithm recursively calls itself with the extended prefix (Line 11). Hereafter, we fix a QoS-extended communicating system S .

Theorem 1 (qSAT is sound and k -bounded complete). *Given a QoS formula $\Phi \in \mathcal{QL}$ and a bound k , `qSAT`(Φ, S, k) returns **true** iff there exists $\pi \in \Delta_S^i$ such that $\langle \pi, \epsilon \rangle \models_S \Phi$, for some $i \leq k$.*

The soundness of **qSAT** immediately follows from the soundness of **qMODELS** (established in Lemma 1 below) which, in turn, relies on the soundness and completeness of **qUNTIL** (cf. Lemmas 2 and 3, respectively). This guarantees that the call to **qMODELS** in Line 5 of **qSAT** returns true iff the run π satisfies Φ . Note that **qSAT** is not guaranteed to be complete due to the bound k .

Lemma 1 (qMODELS is sound and complete). *Given a QoS formula $\Phi \in \mathcal{QL}$ and runs $\pi, \pi' \in \Delta_S$, where $\pi' \in \text{prf}(\pi)$, **qMODELS**(Φ, S, π, π') returns **true** iff $\langle \pi, \pi' \rangle \models_S \Phi$.*

Proof. By structural induction on Φ . If Φ is \top , the result follows trivially. If Φ is an atomic formula, the algorithm computes the aggregation over the run π' (Line 6) and invokes the decision procedure of RCFs to check whether $\text{agg}_S(\pi')$ entails Φ in the theory of real closed fields. If Φ is $\Phi_1 \vee \Phi_2$, the algorithm perform two recursive calls and returns true iff either $\langle \pi, \pi' \rangle \models_S \Phi_1$ or $\langle \pi, \pi' \rangle \models_S \Phi_2$. If Φ is $\Phi_1 \mathcal{U}^G \Phi_2$, the algorithm returns true iff **qUNTIL**($\Phi_1, G, \Phi_2, S, \pi, \pi', \epsilon$) returns true. By Lemmas 2 and 3 this is equivalent to $\langle \pi, \pi' \rangle \models_S \Phi_1 \mathcal{U}^G \Phi_2$. \square

We now prove the soundness and completeness of **qUNTIL**.

Lemma 2 (qUNTIL is sound). *Given a QoS formula $\Phi_1, \Phi_2 \in \mathcal{QL}$, a g-choreography G , and runs π, π', π'' such that*

- a) $\pi' \pi'' \in \text{prf}(\pi)$ and $\pi \in \Delta_S$, and
- b) for all $\pi''' \in \text{prf}(\pi'')$, if $\pi''' \neq \pi''$ then $\langle \pi, \pi' \pi''' \rangle \models_S \Phi_1$

if **qUNTIL**($\Phi_1, G, \Phi_2, S, \pi, \pi', \pi''$) returns **true** then $\langle \pi, \pi' \rangle \models_S \Phi_1 \mathcal{U}^G \Phi_2$.

Proof. The call to **qUNTIL**($\Phi_1, G, \Phi_2, S, \pi, \pi', \pi''$) either reaches Line 3 or it reaches Line 11 and the recursive call returns true. In the first case, we know $\mathcal{L}[\pi''] \in \hat{\mathcal{L}}[G]$ and that **qMODELS**($\Phi_2, S, \pi, \pi' \pi''$) returned true. By Lemma 1 it follows that $\langle \pi, \pi' \pi'' \rangle \models_S \Phi_2$. Together with hypotheses a) and b) the conditions of the semantics of the formula $\Phi_1 \mathcal{U}^G \Phi_2$ (see Definition 6) are met. In the case of reaching Line 11 we know the recursive call **qUNTIL**($\Phi_1, G, \Phi_2, S, \pi, \pi', \pi'' \xrightarrow{\ell} q$) returned true. Conditions a) and b) applied to the input of the recursive call holds because of the way transition $\xrightarrow{\ell} q$ was chosen and the fact that condition on Line 4 returned false. Therefore, we can take the output of the recursive call to satisfy Lemma 2 as an inductive hypothesis and conclude $\langle \pi, \pi' \rangle \models_S \Phi_1 \mathcal{U}^G \Phi_2$. \square

Lemma 3 (Completeness of qUNTIL). *Given a QoS formula $\Phi_1, \Phi_2 \in \mathcal{QL}$, a g-choreography G , and runs π, π', π'' such that*

- a) $\pi' \pi'' \in \text{prf}(\pi)$ and $\pi \in \Delta_S$, and
- b) for all $\pi''' \in \text{prf}(\pi'')$, if $\pi''' \neq \pi''$ then either $\mathcal{L}[\pi'''] \notin \hat{\mathcal{L}}[G]$ or $\langle \pi, \pi' \pi''' \rangle \not\models_S \Phi_2$

if **qUNTIL**($\Phi_1, G, \Phi_2, S, \pi, \pi', \pi''$) returns **false** then $\langle \pi, \pi' \rangle \not\models_S \Phi_1 \mathcal{U}^G \Phi_2$

Proof. The call to $\text{qUNTIL}(\Phi_1, \mathbf{G}, \Phi_2, S, \pi, \pi', \pi'')$ reaches either Line 5, Line 9 or it reaches Line 11 and the recursive call returns false. In all cases, by condition b) we know that no prefix of π'' could be witness of the existential in the semantics of $\Phi_1 \mathcal{U}^{\mathbf{G}} \Phi_2$ (see Definition 6) because it would need to both be in $\hat{\mathcal{L}}[\mathbf{G}]$ and satisfy Φ_2 . Run π'' itself cannot be the witness for the same reasons due to the fact that condition in Line 2 was not met. Which means either $\mathcal{L}[\pi''] \notin \hat{\mathcal{L}}[\mathbf{G}]$ or $\text{qMODELS}(\Phi_2, S, \pi, \pi', \pi'')$ returned false, therefore, using Lemma 1, either $\mathcal{L}[\pi''] \notin \hat{\mathcal{L}}[\mathbf{G}]$ or $\langle \pi, \pi' \pi'' \rangle \not\models_S \Phi_2$. The only remaining possibility is for the witness to be a π^* such that $\pi'' \in \text{prf}(\pi^*)$ and $\pi^* \neq \pi''$. In the case of reaching Line 5, we know that $\text{qMODELS}(\Phi_1, S, \pi, \pi', \pi'')$ returned false. By Lemma 1 it follows that $\langle \pi, \pi' \pi'' \rangle \not\models_S \Phi_1$. Therefore, extension π^* couldn't be a witness for the existential in the semantics of $\Phi_1 \mathcal{U}^{\mathbf{G}} \Phi_2$. In the case of reaching Line 9, candidate extension π^* does not exist or it is not in $\hat{\mathcal{L}}[\mathbf{G}]$. In the case of reaching Line 11, we know that $\text{qUNTIL}(\Phi_1, \mathbf{G}, \Phi_2, S, \pi, \pi', \pi'' \xrightarrow{q})$ returned false. Notice that conditions a) and b) applied to the input of the recursive calls holds because of the way transition \xrightarrow{q} was chosen and that condition in Line 2 was not met. Therefore, we can take the output of the recursive calls to satisfy Lemma 3 as an inductive hypothesis and conclude that $\langle \pi, \pi' \rangle \not\models \Phi_1 \mathcal{U}^{\mathbf{G}} \Phi_2$. \square

Notice that the proof for Lemma 1 uses Lemma 3 and Lemma 2, and that the proofs for Lemma 3 and Lemma 2 use Lemma 1. This does not undermine the soundness of the proofs because the lemmas are always (inductively) applied on smaller \mathcal{QL} formulas. Now that the soundness and completeness of qMODELS and qUNTIL is established, it remains to show their termination. Termination follows from the fact that both the number of logical operators in Φ and the number of transitions in π are finite. The first guarantees qMODELS eventually reaches a base case and the second guarantees qUNTIL eventually reaches a base case. Finally, the base case in qMODELS , computing aggregation and checking entailment in the theory of real closed fields, terminates due to the decidability of RCFs [17].

6.1 A bounded model-checking approach for \mathcal{QL}

Previous results allow for a straightforward bounded model-checking approach for \mathcal{QL} . Like for other model-checking procedures for a language that admits negation, qSAT can be used to check validity of a \mathcal{QL} formula in a system S by checking the satisfiability of the negated formula. This constitutes a counterexample-finding procedure for \mathcal{QL} . The caveat is that qSAT is a k -bounded semidecision procedure rather than a decision procedure. However, restricting to \mathcal{QL}^- , namely \mathcal{QL} formulae that do not contain the $*$ operator in their choreographies, we can find finite models of satisfiable formulae of \mathcal{QL}^- (cf. Theorem 2). Thus, qSAT can serve as a decision procedure for \mathcal{QL}^- , if one computes a suitable bound k .

Theorem 2 (Finite model property of \mathcal{QL}^-). *Given a QoS formula $\Phi \in \mathcal{QL}^-$, and runs $\pi \in \Delta_S^{\infty}$, $\pi' \in \Delta_S$ such that $\pi' \in \text{prf}(\pi)$. If $\langle \pi, \pi' \rangle \models_S \Phi$ then there exists a finite run $\pi^- \in \Delta_S$ such that $\pi^- \in \text{prf}(\pi)$ and $\langle \pi^-, \pi' \rangle \models_S \Phi$.*

Proof. By structural induction on Φ . If Φ is \top or an atomic formula, take $\pi^- = \pi'$. If Φ is $\Phi_1 \vee \Phi_2$, we have that either $\langle \pi, \pi' \rangle \models_S \Phi_1$ or $\langle \pi, \pi' \rangle \models_S \Phi_2$. By inductive hypothesis, either $\langle \pi_1^-, \pi' \rangle \models_S \Phi_1$ or $\langle \pi_2^-, \pi' \rangle \models_S \Phi_2$ for some finite $\pi_1^-, \pi_2^- \in \text{prf}(\pi)$. Therefore, either $\langle \pi_1^-, \pi' \rangle \models_S \Phi_1 \vee \Phi_2$ or $\langle \pi_2^-, \pi' \rangle \models_S \Phi_1 \vee \Phi_2$.

If Φ is $\Phi_1 \mathcal{U}^G \Phi_2$, by Definition 6 we have there exists π'' such that $\pi' \pi'' \in \text{prf}(\pi)$ and $\mathcal{L}[\pi''] \in \mathcal{L}[\mathbf{G}]$, and $\langle \pi, \pi' \pi'' \rangle \models_S \Phi_2$, and for all $\pi''' \in \text{prf}(\pi'')$, if $\pi''' \neq \pi''$ then $\langle \pi, \pi' \pi''' \rangle \models_S \Phi_1$. If we apply the inductive hypothesis to Φ_1 and Φ_2 , we have there exists π'' such that $\pi' \pi'' \in \text{prf}(\pi)$ and $\mathcal{L}[\pi''] \in \mathcal{L}[\mathbf{G}]$, and $\langle \pi_2^-, \pi' \pi'' \rangle \models_S \Phi_2$ for some $\pi_2^- \in \text{prf}(\pi)$, and for all $\pi''' \in \text{prf}(\pi'')$, if $\pi''' \neq \pi''$ then $\langle \pi_1^-, \pi' \pi''' \rangle \models_S \Phi_1$ for some $\pi_1^- \in \text{prf}(\pi)$. Notice that since \mathbf{G} is $*$ -free, run π'' in the language $\mathcal{L}[\mathbf{G}]$ is necessarily finite and so is the number of quantified runs π''' . Therefore, the number of runs π_1^- involved in the previous statement is finite, and there is a maximum among their lengths, so we can take π^- as the longest between π_2^- and runs π_1^- . Since π_2^- and all the π_1^- are prefixes of π , then they will also be prefixes of π^- , and therefore we have the conditions to conclude $\langle \pi^-, \pi' \rangle \models_S \Phi_1 \mathcal{U}^G \Phi_2$.

If the outermost operator in Φ is \neg , we need to consider all the possible cases for the immediate subformula of Φ . If Φ is $\neg\psi$ with ψ atomic formula, we have that $\langle \pi, \pi' \rangle \not\models_S \psi$. It follows that $\langle \pi', \pi' \rangle \not\models_S \psi$ and we can take $\pi^- = \pi'$. If Φ is $\neg(\Phi_1 \vee \Phi_2)$, we have that $\langle \pi, \pi' \rangle \not\models_S \Phi_1 \vee \Phi_2$. It follows that $\langle \pi, \pi' \rangle \not\models_S \Phi_1$ and $\langle \pi, \pi' \rangle \not\models_S \Phi_2$. By inductive hypothesis, there exists $\pi_1^- \in \Delta_S$ such that $\pi_1^- \in \text{prf}(\pi)$ and $\langle \pi_1^-, \pi' \rangle \not\models_S \Phi_1$ and there exists $\pi_2^- \in \Delta_S$ such that $\pi_2^- \in \text{prf}(\pi)$ and $\langle \pi_2^-, \pi' \rangle \not\models_S \Phi_2$. It is enough to take π^- as the longest between π_1^- and π_2^- . If Φ is $\neg(\Phi_1 \mathcal{U}^G \Phi_2)$, we have that $\langle \pi, \pi' \rangle \not\models_S \Phi_1 \mathcal{U}^G \Phi_2$. Therefore, for all π'' such that $\pi' \pi'' \in \text{prf}(\pi)$, if $\mathcal{L}[\pi''] \in \mathcal{L}[\mathbf{G}]$, and $\langle \pi, \pi' \pi'' \rangle \models_S \Phi_2$, then there exists $\pi''' \in \text{prf}(\pi'')$, with $\pi''' \neq \pi''$ such that $\langle \pi, \pi' \pi''' \rangle \models_S \neg\Phi_1$. If we apply the inductive hypothesis to Φ_2 and $\neg\Phi_1$, we have that for all π'' such that $\pi' \pi'' \in \text{prf}(\pi)$, if $\mathcal{L}[\pi''] \in \mathcal{L}[\mathbf{G}]$, and $\langle \pi_2^-, \pi' \pi'' \rangle \models_S \Phi_2$ for some $\pi_2^- \in \Delta_S$ with $\pi_2^- \in \text{prf}(\pi)$, then there exists $\pi''' \in \text{prf}(\pi'')$, with $\pi''' \neq \pi''$ such that $\langle \pi_1^-, \pi' \pi''' \rangle \models_S \neg\Phi_1$ for some $\pi_1^- \in \Delta_S$ with $\pi_1^- \in \text{prf}(\pi)$. Notice that since \mathbf{G} is $*$ -free, any run in the language $\mathcal{L}[\mathbf{G}]$ is necessarily finite. Therefore, there is a maximum among the lengths of the runs π_2^- , and we can take π^- as the longest between π_2^- and π_1^- . \square

The proof of Thm. 2 suggests how to compute a bound on the length of the model π^- that satisfies the lemma. That is, recursively in the structure of Φ by taking the maximum between the bounds of the immediate subformulae and, for the case of the \mathcal{U}^G operator, the length of the longest run in $\mathcal{L}[\mathbf{G}]$. This bound can be used as k in qSAT to obtain a full decision procedure for \mathcal{QL}^- . Searching for counterexamples of an arbitrary formula $\Phi \in \mathcal{QL}$ up to a bounded number of unfoldings of $*$ is equivalent to searching for counterexamples in a formula $\hat{\Phi}$ in \mathcal{QL}^- where each $*$ has been replaced by a finite number of unfoldings. Which means that the bound computed for \mathcal{QL}^- can be used to search for counterexamples in \mathcal{QL} . Notice that qSAT can be easily extended to return the run that satisfies the formula, if there is one. Which can help identify the source of QoS formula violations when used as a counterexample-finding procedure.

7 Conclusions

We presented a framework for the design and analysis of QoS-aware distributed message-passing systems using choreographies and a general model of QoS. We tackle this problem by: 1) abstractly representing QoS attributes as symbols denoting real values, whose behaviour is completely captured by a decidable RCFs theory, 2) extending the choreographic model of CFSM by associating QoS specifications to each state of the machine, 3) introducing \mathcal{QL} , a logic based on *DLTL*, for expressing QoS properties with a straightforward satisfaction relation based on runs of communicating systems, and 4) giving a semi-decision procedure for \mathcal{QL} and defining a decidable fragment \mathcal{QL}^- that allowed us to give a bounded model-checking procedure for the full logic. A prototype implementation of our procedure is under development. It relies on the SMT solver Z3 [34] for the satisfiability of the QoS constraints in atomic formulae and on ChorGram [35,36] for the semantics of g-choreographies and CFSMs. An interesting by-product of our framework is that it could be used for the monitoring of local computations to check at run-time if they stay in the constraint of QoS specifications. If static guarantees on QoS specifications are not possible, run-time monitors can be easily attained by adapting techniques for monitor generation from behavioural types [37,38].

We identify two further main future research directions. On the one hand, there is the theoretical question of whether \mathcal{QL} is decidable or not. In this respect, the similarity of \mathcal{QL} with *DLTL* (cf. Section 2) hints towards an affirmative answer suggesting that the problem can be resolved to emptiness of Büchi automata [39] corresponding to \mathcal{QL} formulae. However, the decidability of \mathcal{QL} is not so easy to attain. In general, a \mathcal{QL} formula may yield an infinite state space due to instantiation of QoS attributes. On the other hand, the usability of the framework could be improved through two extensions of \mathcal{QL} and a less demanding way of modeling QoS-extended communicating systems. The first extension of \mathcal{QL} are *selective* aggregation, enabling the aggregation of QoS attributes only for some specific states of runs. This can be done by extending the grammar of g-choreographies given in Definition 1 with an extra production of the shape $G ::= \dots \mid [G]$, “bracketing” the part of the choreography relevant for the aggregation. Notice that the run still has to match the whole choreography. A second extension of \mathcal{QL} is the introduction of *wildcards* as a mechanism to “ignore” a subchoreography. Syntactically, it can be represented by, once again, extending the grammar given in Definition 1 with an extra production, with shape $G ::= \dots \mid _$, where $_$ is interpreted as a wildcard and plays the role of matching any possible g-choreography. In this case, the shape of the part of the run that matches the wildcard is disregarded but attributes are aggregated along the whole run. Finally, a less demanding way of modeling QoS-extended systems could be achieved by extending g-choreographies with QoS specifications annotating specific interactions and extending the projection of g-choreographies into CFSMs taking into account such annotations.

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